

CHARACTERISATION OF EMBEDDED CHANNEL NETWORKS IN CFRPS FOR ACTIVE COOLING

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ABSTRACT

Carbon fibre-reinforced polymers have inherently poor thermal properties, driven by their anisotropic structure and the relatively low thermal conductivity of their constituent materials, particularly the matrix phase. This makes them unfit for use in structures surrounding heat emitting components in aircraft. This low thermal performance can potentially be mitigated via active fluid cooling through embedded networks of channels within the composite structure. In order to explore the fundamental thermal management capabilities of this approach, embedded channel networks have been fabricated and thermally tested, with the performance compared against numerical results from COMSOL Multiphysics. The channel networks were manufactured within CFRP samples by embedding metallic wires along the neutral axis during prepreg hand layup and extracting them post-cure, with fluid fittings bonded into the inlets and outlets of each channel. The samples were thermally characterised under conductive thermal loads applied via a heating mat with increasing flow rates of coolant pumped through the channels. A range of sample and channel geometries and process parameters were tested to understand their impact on thermal performance, with particular interest in the effect of channel number and diameter, flow rate, and coolant temperature. The experiments show that up to an 80% reduction in surface temperature can be achieved through active cooling, with improvements driven by increasing the flow rate and channel volume fraction. A higher number of channels within the sample is also shown to create a more uniform temperature profile, removing hot spots on the surface. Thermal modelling results were validated against the experimental results, showing good agreement.

1 INTRODUCTION

At ambient temperatures, carbon fibre-reinforced polymers exhibit excellent mechanical properties and an especially high strength-to-weight ratio that makes them ideal for use in primary structures in aircraft. A typical aerospace-grade CFRP system can be up to seven times stronger and two times stiffer than its aluminium counterpart at only two thirds the weight, with relative performance being highest when the loads are directly aligned with the fibres [1]. However, CFRPs have comparatively poor thermal properties and low maximum service temperatures which make them unsuitable for any application where they may be exposed to significantly elevated temperatures or high thermal loads. While carbon fibres themselves exhibit moderate to high thermal conductivity (5-15 W/mK for PAN-based fibres, 500-1000 W/mK for pitch-based fibres)[2-5], the much lower conductivity of the resin matrix (0.19-0.25 W/mK) [6,7] and the anisotropy of their structure means the net conductivity for a

typical CFRP layup is somewhere in the region of 4-5 W/mK in the in-plane direction and only around 1-2 W/mK in the out-of-plane direction, much lower than a typical aerospace aluminium alloy (~230 W/mK) [8-10]. This combines with glass transition temperatures typically in the range of 150-200°C, with even lower working temperatures quoted by manufacturers due to safety factors [11]. As a result, metallics such as aluminium or magnesium alloys are still the preferred materials for aerospace structures that must withstand high levels of thermal loading, such as electric generators and gearboxes.

Several concepts have been explored to improve the thermal properties of CFRPs including fillers, coatings and crystal structure alignment [12-14]. While these passive techniques do offer some improvement in thermal conductivity, they come at the expense of increased manufacturing and materials costs, added complexity, and still do not achieve the levels of thermal conductivity needed for many real-world applications. Instead of attempting to improve the inherent thermal properties of the CFRP system, it is attractive to consider active approaches for removing heat from the structure, for example through the use of an embedded system of channels permeated by a heat transfer fluid. This technique was first inspired by biological systems that exhibit intricate microvascular networks such as leaves or the human circulatory system and was hypothesised as a means of adding multifunctionality to a structure [15,16]. Active cooling has since been determined as one such function and has been investigated both experimentally and numerically over the last 15 years by a small number of researchers [17-23]. For instance, Pety *et al* [20] achieved up to 80% cooling efficiency (proportion of heat removed over the heat applied) in composite panels with embedded channels at flow rates up to 30 ml/min, and Coppola *et al* [17] observed a 90% retention of mechanical properties in specimen subjected to 4-point bending up to 325 °C. While the results from these studies show effective and repeatable channel fabrication, highly efficient cooling, good retention of mechanical properties, and a large scope for optimisation, the approach has not yet made it into widespread use, in part because it has never been thoroughly characterised with regards to the numerous design and process parameters that impact the effectiveness of heat removal.

This paper attempts to carry out a thorough characterisation of channel cooling performance using a broad-spectrum design of experiments, backed up by numerical analysis, to directly measure the impact of varying the key design and operating parameters within the channel network architecture. CFRP samples containing embedded channels are first manufactured with various combinations of thicknesses, channel diameters and channel pitches. The samples are then thermally tested via conduction with respect to process parameters such as flow rate, coolant fluid, and coolant fluid temperature. The results of these experiments are then discussed to analyse the effect of these parameters on cooling performance. Finally, numerical models are set up in COMSOL Multiphysics to validate against the experimental data obtained, with the models then being ready to explore a wider and more complex design space in future work.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Channel fabrication

Previous work has explored numerous approaches to fabricate embedded channels within a composite, including hollow glass fibres or steel tubes, solder removal, direct ink writing, and vapourisation of sacrificial materials (VaSC) [24-31]. However, in this work, manual wire extraction (MWE) was chosen as the preferred fabrication method due to the comparative ease of the process and because there is no requirement for post-cure treatments. MWE involves embedding high tensile strength wires within the composite structure during hand layup and removing them post-cure by pulling them out manually, leaving a hollow channel of inverse shape embedded within the composite structure [32-34]. With this method, several wires could be embedded to create a network of straight and flat channels within the CFRP, each with its own inlet and outlet.

Figure 1 – a) Wire positioning jig in place over a laminate before cure b) post-cured sample with wires removed and syringe tips glued into inlet and outlet

In this work, PTFE-coated nickel-chromium (Nichrome) wires of two different diameters (0.57 mm and 0.97 mm) were used, and they were embedded at the midplane of IM7/8552 prepreg CFRP laminates during hand lay up. For both of the specimen thicknesses manufactured (2 mm and 4 mm), the ply stacking sequence was such that the wires would be entirely contained within plies orientated parallel to the channels (0° direction) to allow for the thickness of the channel to be accommodated within the layup through movement of the adjacent fibres with minimal disturbance of the off-axis plies above and below the midplane. In all cases, a large laminate (300 x 300 mm) was prepared and a series of wires (0.57 mm or 0.97 mm) at set pitches were strung across the midplane and held in place using an MDF jig with laser cut indexing holes to position screws around which the wires ends were wrapped (Figure 1a). The laminates were then cured in an autoclave under vacuum at the standard IM7/8552 cure cycle (2 °C/min ramp up to 110 °C, 60-minute dwell, 2 °C/min ramp up to 180 °C, 120-minute dwell, then cool down to ambient temperature with a vent of pressure at 60 °C). After curing, the laminate was heated to approximately 50 °C on a hot plate to help loosen the wires, which were manually pulled out using pliers, leaving a set of hollow channels. Finally, the large laminate was cut into smaller individual test samples (120 x 24 mm) and syringe tips (18G for 0.57 mm, 20G for 0.97 mm) were glued into the exposed channel ends using 2-part epoxy (Araldite), as shown in Figure 1b.

In order to test a large array of geometry-based parameters, laminates of thicknesses 2 mm and 4 mm were manufactured, and the wires were spaced such that the resulting collection of samples would have instances containing networks of two, three, and five evenly spaced channels. The combination of channel diameter, laminate thickness, and channel number gave rise to nine distinct sets of samples, with differing channel volume fractions, defined as the cross-sectional area of the channels in a specimen divided by its full cross-sectional area, as enumerated in Table 1.

Table 1 – Geometric parameters of samples tested

Laminate thickness [mm]	Channel diameter [mm]	Number of channels	Channel volume fraction [%]
2	0.57	2	1.08
		3	1.62
		5	2.70
4	0.57	2	0.54
		3	0.81
		5	1.35
	0.97	2	1.54
		3	2.31
		5	3.85

2.2 Thermal testing

The manufactured specimens were tested on a custom thermal conduction test rig (Figure 2). They were first placed on a silicone heater mat (from Under Control Instruments) at a set heat flux and allowed to reach steady-state temperature. The time history of the temperature distributions on the entire top surface of the specimens was tracked and captured with an IR camera (FLIR T650sc). Water at a prescribed initial temperature was then circulated through the embedded channels at a set flow rate using silicone tubing and a peristaltic pump (Watson-Marlow 503U). The water was maintained close to the desired temperature using a water bath (Grant JB Nova 12L) and was allowed to circulate around the channels until steady-state temperature was again reached. The flow rate was then increased to test the next flow condition, which was tracked with a flow meter (Omega FLR1008-D). K-type thermocouples and wet/wet pressure sensors (Omega PX26-15GV) were attached to the silicone tubing just before and after the inlet and outlet of the specimens, and the temperatures and pressures were captured using National Instruments data acquisition modules (NI 9212, NI 9219) and LabVIEW software.

Figure 2 – Schematic of conduction test setup

Each specimen was tested at three flow rates (10, 20 and 30 ml/min) and three heat fluxes (500, 1000 and 1500 W/m²), resulting in eighty-one separate experiments. Two sample geometries (4 mm thickness, 0.97 mm channel diameter, two and three-channels) were also chosen for further testing with higher flow rates (up to 70 ml/min), different initial water temperatures (10, 30 °C), and different coolant fluids (deionised water, mono-propylene glycol). For conciseness in this paper, the 4mm thick specimens with 0.97 mm channel diameter have been chosen as the baseline data set, with comparisons made to the other geometries.

2.3 Computational modelling

Models representing the same geometries and process parameters used in the experiments were set up in COMSOL Multiphysics using the heat transfer in solid and fluids design module. A solid body of 120 x 24 mm (4 mm and 2 mm thickness) was designed to represent the specimens with a second body of 120 x 24 x 0.5 mm was created in contact with the bottom surface of the main body to represent the heater mat. Two, three, and five-channels were then modelled with diameters 0.228 mm and 0.485 mm along the neutral axis of the main body at the desired pitches (4 mm, 6 mm, 8 mm). An example two-channel model is shown in Figure 3. The main body was assigned a custom material representing IM7/8852, with properties obtained from the material datasheet and previous experiments [35]. Built-in

material properties were used for water and silicone for the fluid channels and heater mat respectively. A full breakdown of process parameters and material properties is shown in Table 2.

Figure 3 – Meshed COMSOL model of a two-channel specimen with 0.97 mm diameter channels

A heat source was applied to the heater mat domain to represent the desired heat flux. This was converted to raw power using Equation 1 below. External natural convection and surface-to-ambient radiation were applied to all exposed surfaces of the specimen. The channels within the specimen were grouped together and assigned a desired inlet temperature and flow rate. A global tetrahedral mesh was generated around the model, with a finer triangular mesh around the channels (548,278 total elements).

Table 2 – Parameters, model inputs and material properties for COMSOL models

Specimen Geometry	Value	Description
l	120 [mm]	Length of specimen
w	24 [mm]	Width of specimen
t	2, 4 [mm]	Thickness of specimen
r	0.285, 0.485 [mm]	Channel radius
p	4, 6, 8 [mm]	Distance between channels
Model inputs		
T_a	21-26 [°C]	Ambient temperature
T_c	14-28 [°C]	Coolant fluid inlet temperature
Q	8-33 [ml/min]	Flow rate of fluid
P	6.573-17.190 [W]	Power applied ^a
L_t	10 [mm]	Characteristic length of top surface ^b
L_s	0.984, 1.936 [mm]	Characteristic length of sides ^b
L_e	0.923, 1.714 [mm]	Characteristic length of top edges ^b
Material properties		
ρ_c	1570 [kg/m ³]	Density of IM7/8552 [35]
Cp_c	920 [kJ/kgK]	Specific heat capacity of IM7/8552 [35]
k_c	1.750 [W/mK]	Thermal conductivity of IM7/8552 ^c
ϵ	0.970	Surface emissivity
ρ_w	~ 998 [kg/m ³]	Density of water ^d
Cp_w	~ 4.180 [kJ/kgK]	Specific heat capacity of water ^d
k_w	0.600 [W/mK]	Thermal conductivity of water
ρ_s	1100 [kg/m ³]	Density of heater mat (silicone rubber)
Cp_s	1.900 [kJ/kgK]	Specific heat capacity of heater mat
k_s	0.500 [W/mK]	Thermal conductivity heater mat

^aConverted from heat flux values

^bFor external natural convection. Defined as area of surface divided by perimeter

^cObtained from previous, unpublished study

^dTemperature dependent

$$P = (\sqrt{Q''RA}) * I \quad (1)$$

Where P is power, Q'' is heat flux, R is resistance of the heater mat, A is surface area of the specimen, and I is the current of the heater mat.

The model outputs mirrored those in the experimental test: maximum temperature of the top surface; average temperature of the top surface; and outlet temperature of the fluid. The temperature profile of the model could also be captured and directly compared to the profile from the IR images. Instead of taking generic or desired parameters (e.g. $T_a=21^\circ\text{C}$, $T_c=20^\circ\text{C}$, $Q=10$ ml/min) the model was set up with actual dataset specific values for ambient temperature, inlet temperature and flow rate that were captured throughout the experimental tests. This results in a model output for each individual test rather than general model results to compare against.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During testing, the ambient temperature in the lab fluctuated depending on the outside temperature and the time of day, and this had a non-negligible effect on the temperature of the coolant fluid at the inlet to the channels, and to a lesser extent is likely to have affected the heat transferred out of the specimens. To account for the change in ambient temperature across different testing runs and datasets, the results are normalized to inlet temperature using a ratio derived from the inlet temperature and no-flow heating condition. This ratio (“effective cooling”) is defined in Equation 2 below and describes the actual temperature reduction of the specimen over the maximum theoretical temperature reduction, based on the idea that the specimen temperature can approach but never be cooler than the coolant inlet temperature.

$$e_c = \left(\frac{T_{max,nf} - T_{max,Q}}{T_{max,nf} - T_{inlet}} \right) * 100 \quad (2)$$

Where e_c is the effective cooling, $T_{max,nf}$ is the maximum surface temperature of the specimen in the no-flow condition, $T_{max,Q}$ is the maximum surface temperature of the specimen for a given flow rate, and T_{inlet} is the temperature of the coolant supplied to the inlet of the channels.

The inlet and outlet temperatures could further be used to calculate a heat removal rate from the specimen, and this could then be compared to the power supplied to the specimen from the heater mat to give heat removal rate as a proportion, as shown in Equations 3 and 4.

$$q = \sum_n (Q\rho Cp\Delta T) \quad (3)$$

$$H_{\%} = \left(\frac{q}{P_m} \right) * 100 \quad (4)$$

Where q is the rate of heat removal, Q is the flow rate, ρ is coolant density, Cp is coolant specific heat capacity, ΔT is the temperature difference across the inlet and outlet of the channels, n is number of channels, $H_{\%}$ is the heat removal proportion, and P_m is the power supplied to the heater mat.

3.1 Effect of flow rate

The maximum surface temperatures and the effective cooling of two datasets are shown in Figure 4. In all samples, both the maximum and average surface temperatures decreased as flow rate increased. This began with a steep initial decrease from the no flow condition to the lowest flow rate (10 ml/min) with more marginal reductions as the flow rate was further increased. The levelling off of the effective cooling suggests that merely the presence of coolant at a minimal flow rate (10 ml/min is relatively low and easily achievable with most commercial pumps) is sufficient to cool the sample significantly. The best performing specimen geometry was observed to be the 4 mm thickness with 0.97 mm channel diameter, which exhibits up to a 116 °C (80%) decrease in maximum surface temperature at the highest flow rate (30 ml/min), number of channels (five), and applied heat flux (1500 W/m²). This is expected considering this configuration contains the highest channel volume fraction. However, the 4 mm, 0.57 mm specimen still exhibits a substantial surface temperature reduction (63 °C) even at the lowest flow rate (10 ml/min), number of channels (two), and applied heat flux (500 W/m²).

Figure 4 – Maximum surface temperature and effective cooling of specimen of all geometries and a) two-channels at 500 W/m² applied heat flux b) five-channels at 1500 W/m² applied heat flux

The temperature difference between the inlet and the outlet decreases as flow rate increases, largely due to the increased velocity in the fluid through the channel. Despite this, the heat removal proportion increases as flow rate increases, due to the fact that the increase in the flow rate outweighs the drop in temperature difference. The heat removal rates are shown in Figure 5.

Higher flow rates were tested in two and three-channel samples from the batch of specimens of 4 mm thickness and 0.97 mm channel diameter, the results of which are shown in Figure 6. Increasing the flow rate beyond 30 ml/min appears to have very little effect on further reducing the maximum surface temperature, with reductions below 0.5°C from successive flow rate increases. Increasing the flow rate above 30 ml/min does however have a significant effect on the pressure experienced across the sample (see Figure 8b in Section 3.5), leading to difficult testing conditions where the high pressure may cause leaks at the syringe/adhesive interface or in the silicone tubing. It was determined that increasing the flow rate beyond 30 ml/min is unnecessary from a cooling perspective and prohibitive from a pressure perspective, especially in the specimen containing 0.57mm diameter channels, where pressure is inherently higher to increased flow restriction.

Figure 5 – Heat removal rate and heat removal proportion of specimens of all geometries and a) two-channels at 500 W/m² applied heat flux b) five-channels at 1500 W/m² applied heat flux

Figure 6 – Maximum surface temperature and effective cooling in a 4 mm, 0.97 mm specimen with two and three-channels at 500 W/m²

3.2 Effect of pitch

Similar to flow rate, reducing the pitch and therefore increasing the number of channels within a sample leads to a higher reduction in maximum and average surface temperatures across all samples tested. More importantly in this case, and as seen in Table 3, having more channels in a specimen leads to a smaller difference between the maximum and average surface temperatures, giving a more uniform temperature distribution across the top surface.

An increased number of channels also leads to increased heat removal from the specimen, with a 10-12% increase from a two to a three-channel specimen and a similar gain from a three to a five-channel specimen. Using the images captured by the IR camera, the temperature profiles of specimens with the same process parameters but a different number of channels can be compared directly, as seen in Figure 7a. It is observed that there is not only a lower temperature on the surface as the number of channels increases, but also less variation in colour across the top surface. For instance, the two-channel sample clearly exhibits hotter regions either side of the channels towards the edge of the specimen. These are minimised by the three-channel specimen and completely eliminated by the five-channel specimen, leading to a more uniform temperature profile. This effect is also clearly reflected in the standard deviations of temperature across the specimens (Table 3), which have a consistent decreasing trend with increasing numbers of channels for all specimen geometries.

Table 3 – Temperature difference and standard deviation for all specimen geometries at 20 ml/min and 1000 W/m² applied heat flux

Specimen geometry [mm]	Number of channels	Maximum temperature [°C]	Average temperature [°C]	Temperature difference [°C]	Standard deviation [°C]
4 thickness, 0.97 diameter	2	37.48	32.32	5.16	1.66
	3	32.14	29.42	2.72	1.07
	5	28.64	27.29	1.35	0.62
4 thickness, 0.57 diameter	2	41.12	36.06	5.06	2.29
	3	36.25	32.19	4.06	1.24
	5	29.86	27.25	2.61	0.71
2 thickness, 0.57 diameter	2	42.43	34.8	7.63	2.35
	3	37.44	31.28	6.16	2.24
	5	30.01	26.65	3.51	0.85

Figure 7 – a) Surface temperature profiles of 4 mm thickness, 0.97 mm channel diameter specimens of two, three and five-channels at 20 ml/min and 1000 W/m² b) maximum surface temperature of a 4 mm thickness, 0.97 mm channel diameter, two-channel specimen at all heat fluxes in no-flow condition and at 10 ml/min

3.3 High heat flux

The no-flow condition can only be tested experimentally up to 1500 W/m² due to the temperatures on the specimen (~154 °C on a 2 mm thickness specimen) approaching and even exceeding the maximum rated operating temperature of the heater mat (150 °C), in addition to potential damage to the composite. As such, higher applied heat fluxes were tested in flow on conditions only, with the no-flow condition instead obtained through numerical modelling. As seen in Figure 7b, even when increasing the heat flux to 3500 W/m², which would result in a predicted maximum surface temperature of ~190 °C, the presence of cooling fluid at the lowest flow rate and number of channels is still sufficient to reduce the maximum surface temperature markedly.

The higher heat fluxes were chosen based on potential applications in industry, as seen in Table 4. In all cases, the maximum surface temperature was reduced to below the maximum operating temperatures associated with these applications. This suggests that a composite structure with embedded channels could be substituted for the existing metallic casings of these components without compromising the working conditions of the component itself.

Table 4 – Application specific working temperatures and achieved cooling in a 4mm thickness, 0.97mm channel diameter, two-channel specimen

Heat flux [W/m ²]	Application	Critical temperature [°C]	Maximum temperature no-flow [°C]	Maximum temperature flow [°C]	Temperature difference [°C]
500	EV battery	55	102.81	30.79	24.21
2200	Transmission shaft	85	164.48	38.88	46.12
3000	Transmission gear	90	181.00	41.12	48.88
3500	Transmission bearing	90	189.84	42.74	47.26

3.4 Effect of coolant fluid and temperature

Deionised water and a 50:50 mixture of water and mono-propylene glycol were also tested as coolant fluids, as well as different inlet temperatures of water. As seen in the results in Figure 8a, cooling the water to below room temperature (~10 °C) leads to an increased surface temperature reduction, with the opposite effect occurring when the water is instead heated (~30 °C). In both these cases however, it was

challenging to maintain the target temperature, as the water would heat or cool as it left the water bath and was pumped through the tubing towards the specimen. As a result, the actual inlet temperature was on average $\sim 16^\circ\text{C}$ for the 10°C test and $\sim 27^\circ\text{C}$ for the 30°C test. Despite this, there is still a significant improvement in temperature reduction in the sample if the coolant fluid is first cooled, and this could be a significant factor if the inlet temperature can be properly maintained.

Figure 8 - a) Maximum surface temperatures of a 4 mm, 0.97 mm, two-channel specimen at 1500 W/m^2 and 10 ml/min with various coolant fluids and inlet temperatures, and b) pressure differences in all two-channel specimen geometries at 500 W/m^2 at all flow rates

Changing the coolant fluid from tap water to deionised water led to a very small ($\sim 0.5^\circ\text{C}$) reduction in surface temperature in a specimen heated at 500 W/m^2 . This was not significant enough to justify the added complexity of introducing deionised water to the cooling system. Somewhat surprisingly, the water/glycol mixture led to a higher maximum surface temperature in comparative samples. This may be due to the mixture having higher inlet temperature ($\sim 27^\circ\text{C}$) than the standard water ($\sim 21^\circ\text{C}$) due to the initial temperature of the mono-propylene glycol. Despite this disparity in inlet temperature, the glycol/water mixture still exhibits a lower effective cooling than both tap water and deionised water. However, further tests will be performed with the glycol/water mixture at inlet temperatures more in line with the other test fluids.

3.5 Pressure

The pressure difference across the specimen is a significant factor in the testing, as a high-pressure difference can lead to difficulties with the apparatus, namely lower pumping efficiency, leaks at the syringes, or bursts in the silicone tubing. The pressure differences exhibited in the specimens of all geometries are shown in Figure 8b. In general, the inlet pressure will increase as flow rate increases across all specimens. Specimens containing 0.57 mm diameter channels will exhibit up to a twenty-fold increase in inlet pressure compared to specimen containing 0.97 mm diameter channels. Generally, there is minimal change in pressure difference across a specimen as the applied heat flux increases. However, the pressure difference decreases as the number of channels increases. A comparison of applied heat flux, flow rate and number of channels is shown in Table 5.

Table 5 – Pressure difference in a 4 mm thickness, 0.97 mm channel diameter specimen at various applied heat fluxes, flow rates, and number of channels

Applied Heat flux [W/m ²]	Number of channels	Pressure difference [kpa]		
		10 [ml/min]	20 [ml/min]	30 [ml/min]
500	2	4.14	9.17	16.27
	3	3.44	9.24	16.41
	5	2.83	8.83	13.10
1000	2	4.69	9.51	16.13
	3	3.38	9.24	16.96
	5	3.86	8.76	15.58
1500	2	4.83	10.00	16.27
	3	3.31	8.96	16.20
	5	2.96	8.82	15.58

3.6 Numerical modelling

In all instances, the experimental data was compared against the predicted results from the COMSOL models. The experimental results for maximum surface temperature, average surface temperature and outlet temperature are within 10% of the same metric in COMSOL for all datasets. In general, the outlet temperature shows the most agreement with the COMSOL results (within 0.5-3.5 %) and the average surface temperature shows the least (2.5-9.5 %). A more detailed comparison for a 4 mm thickness, 0.97 mm diameter specimen with 5-channels is shown in Figure 9a.

Figure 9 – a) Experimental and simulated temperatures of a 4 mm, 0.97 mm, five-channel specimen at 1500 W/m² and 10 ml/min b) Experimental and simulated top surface temperature profiles of a 4 mm, 0.97 mm, five-channel specimen at 1500 W/m² and 10 ml/min

The COMSOL models can also be used to compare the simulated temperature profiles to those captured with the IR camera, as shown in Figure 9b. There is good visual agreement with several features, showing for instance that the specimen is hotter on the outlet side than the inlet side, as the fluid heats as it traverses the specimen.

4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

This work undertook a combined experimental and numerical campaign to explore the ability of composite plates to be actively fluid cooled through the use of embedded channels. A large number of specimens were manufactured and tested to explore the impact of the key geometrical and operating parameters on the cooling performance achievable, which was considered in terms of both surface temperature reduction and heat flux.

The results show that embedded channels allow for highly effective cooling of the composite specimens even at low coolant flow rates and channel volume fractions. Higher flow rates and an increasing number of channels improve the effectiveness of this cooling, both in terms of maximum temperature reduction and in terms of temperature uniformity. Other parameters such as channel diameter and coolant fluid type play a lesser role. With the correct combination of parameters, composite systems can be successfully cooled to safe working temperatures based on application specific thermal loads, as evidenced in the high heat flux tests. However, pressure difference and inlet temperature of the fluid must be accurately regulated.

The COMSOL models have been validated against the experimental data and can now be used to explore a more complex design space with alternative channel architectures containing 2D shapes, branches and multi-layered sections. These will be designed in COMSOL to test their effectiveness and suitability before being manufactured and tested experimentally.

The existing specimens will be further tested to be fully characterised thermally, with particular attention taken to the effect of inlet temperature and coolant fluid. The specimens will also be mechanically characterised through tensile testing to determine the impact that the presence of the channels have on mechanical properties of the composite under various loading scenarios.

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